

Aerosol-cloud Interactions: Overcoming a Barrier to Projecting Near-term Climate Evolution and Risk

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59 **Key Points:**

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- 61 • Aerosol-cloud interactions remain a barrier to provide precise and actionable advice to
62 policy makers at global and regional levels.
 - 63 • We recommend improving satellite retrievals, expanding ground-based measurements,
64 refining climate models, and advancing machine learning.
 - 65 • Collaboration across research communities will enhance understanding of ACI, the
66 climate projections and policy recommendations.

67 **Abstract**

68 Aerosol–cloud interactions (ACI) are a major source of uncertainty in climate science, critically
69 affecting our ability to project near-term climate evolution and assess societal risks. These
70 interactions influence effective radiative forcing, cloud dynamics, and precipitation patterns,
71 yet remain insufficiently constrained due to limitations in observations, modeling, and process
72 understanding. This uncertainty hampers robust policy advice across multiple domains—from
73 estimating remaining carbon budgets and climate sensitivity, to anticipating regional extreme
74 events and evaluating climate interventions such as solar radiation modification. In many cases,
75 the influence of ACI is either underappreciated or excluded from decision-making frameworks
76 due to its complexity and lack of quantification.

77 This perspective outlines a path forward to overcome these barriers by leveraging emerging
78 opportunities in satellite remote sensing, ground-based and airborne observations, high-
79 resolution climate modeling, and machine learning. We identify key areas where rapid progress
80 is feasible, including improved retrievals of cloud microphysical properties, better
81 representation of natural aerosols in a warming world, and enhanced integration of
82 observational and modeling communities. Even as anthropogenic aerosol and its impacts on
83 clouds is reducing owing to emissions controls, addressing ACI uncertainties remains essential
84 for refining climate projections, supporting effective mitigation and adaptation strategies, and
85 delivering actionable science to policymakers in a rapidly changing climate system.

86 **1 Introduction**

87 The atmosphere is laden with suspended liquid or solid aerosol particles of nano- to
88 micron-sizes. Aerosols are either emitted directly into the atmosphere - primary aerosols (e.g.,
89 dust, sea salt, soot), or form through chemical reactions of precursor gases - secondary aerosols
90 (e.g., sulfates, nitrates, organics). Aerosols impact the radiative balance directly by
91 absorbing/scattering radiation (aerosol-radiation interactions: ARI) or indirectly through
92 aerosol-cloud interactions (ACI).

93 The effective radiative forcing from aerosol–radiation interactions is estimated to be –
94 0.3 W m^{-2} (very likely range -0.6 to 0.0 W m^{-2} ; medium confidence) according to IPCC AR6
95 (Forster et al., 2021), indicating a net cooling that partly offsets greenhouse gas warming.
96 Uncertainty remains high due to variations in aerosol composition, vertical distribution, and
97 regional emission patterns, though it has narrowed compared to AR5 as constraints from
98 satellite and surface radiation data improved. Recent assessments give a total aerosol forcing
99 around -0.85 W m^{-2} [-1.65 to -0.25] (Forster et al., 2025) with ARI contributing roughly one-
100 quarter of the magnitude and the remaining uncertainty arising from aerosol–cloud
101 interactions (Bellouin et al., 2020a; Smith et al., 2023). Regionally, TOA ARI exerts up to -2 to -4
102 W m^{-2} (Szopa et al., 2021; Kasoar et al., 2018) over polluted areas in South and East Asia but is
103 minimal elsewhere, producing hemispheric asymmetries (Loeb et al., 2025) that have affected
104 monsoons and precipitation (Li et al., 2016). Many studies have shown that the surface forcing
105 can be much larger of opposite signs with that inside the atmospheric column due to the trade-
106 off between surface cooling and atmospheric warming. Such a contrast has very significant
107 implications for atmospheric dynamics and convection due to drastically altered temperature

108 lapse rate. This is especially strong in Asia, e.g. $-14/14 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over the Indian Ocean
109 (Ramanathan et al., 2001b) and $-20/18 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ across China (Li et al., 2010). Because ARI's
110 cooling is short-lived, rapid aerosol emission reductions will unmask $\sim 0.1\text{--}0.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ of near-term
111 global warming unless accompanied by deep greenhouse-gas cuts (Forster et al., 2021), giving a
112 total masking of ~ 0.5 together with ACI. The remainder of this perspective will focus on aerosol-
113 cloud interactions, which globally induces a larger cooling compared to ARI, and with a larger
114 uncertainty (AR6).

115 Aerosols alter cloud properties by acting as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN), affecting
116 cloud droplet concentrations (Kohler, 1936) and size (Twomey, 1956), or as ice nucleating
117 particles (INPs: Murray et al., 2021), influencing ice production and cloud phase (liquid/ice
118 amount). Clouds are highly efficient at scattering and absorbing radiation, playing a major role
119 in Earth's energy budget. Anthropogenic aerosol-cloud interactions perturb the global radiation
120 balance, termed Effective Radiative Forcing (ERF) of aerosol-cloud interactions (ERF_{aci}). This
121 includes changes in cloud albedo, water content, and cloud fraction CF. The IPCC's AR6 report
122 (Forster et al., 2021) estimates ERF_{aci} at -1.0 W m^{-2} , about half the ERF magnitude of CO₂
123 increases over the industrial era (1.98 W m^{-2} ; 1750-2014). However, the wide 90% confidence
124 interval (-1.7 to -0.3 W m^{-2}) makes ERF_{aci} the largest contributor to historical ERF uncertainty,
125 and hence to anthropogenic surface temperature change (Figure 1). Despite decades of
126 research, knowledge gaps in ACI remain (Forster et al., 2021; Seinfeld et al., 2016). Modeling
127 and observational evidence in AR6 support the negative ERF_{aci} estimate, suggesting aerosols
128 mask a portion of greenhouse gas-driven warming. Progress since AR5 has improved scientific
129 confidence from low to medium.

130 Human activities emit large amounts of aerosols and precursors, augmenting natural
131 sources. Anthropogenic aerosols significantly modify cloud properties, as evident in ship
132 (Conover, 1966) and aircraft tracks (Well, 1919), and downwind of industrial facilities (Hobbs et
133 al., 1970; Toll et al., 2024), and settlements (Rosenfeld & Woodley, 2000). Natural sources of
134 aerosols such as volcanoes are found to significantly modify cloud properties (Toll et al., 2017).
135 Recent research highlights that decreasing anthropogenic aerosols reduces their masking effect
136 on greenhouse gas-induced warming (Quaas et al., 2022; Diamond, 2023). Air quality
137 regulations will likely further reduce primary aerosol emissions (Turnock et al., 2020), leading to
138 changes in cloud properties under cleaner aerosol conditions. Natural aerosols (e.g., fire
139 aerosols, dust, secondary organic aerosols) may thus play a greater role, creating
140 heterogeneous climate forcing distinct from greenhouse gases (Persad et al., 2022). Regional
141 and temporal heterogeneity in aerosol impacts necessitates understanding aerosol-cloud cycles
142 across different regimes to improve projections.

143 ERF_{aci} uncertainty arises from its dependence on cloud type. Current assessments focus
144 on large-scale clouds, while effects on convective clouds, which involve significant
145 uncertainties, are not fully integrated into global climate models (Stier et al., 2024). AR6
146 acknowledges that the main part of the assessed ERF is for liquid-water clouds, and that ACI in
147 ice/mixed-phase clouds are much less constrained (e.g. Mülmenstädt & Feingold, 2018). Small-
148 scale observations and process models provide insights but are challenging to scale globally
149 (Bellouin et al., 2020b). Long-term measurements of aerosols, CCN, and INPs remain sparse,

150 especially over under sampled regions, like much of the Global South, and remote areas such as
151 the Southern Ocean. While it is evident that the scarcity of aerosol in these remote regions
152 strongly feeds back on cloud properties, the involved process chains are still debated on
153 (Radenz et al., 2021; He et al., 2025). Major uncertainties persist in INP observations, modeling
154 source strengths, the role of in-cloud turbulence, and ice formation processes at warmer
155 subzero temperatures, where ice crystal concentrations often exceed INP concentrations by
156 orders of magnitude (Georgakaki et al., 2022; Wieder et al., 2022). The sensitivity of clouds to
157 warm-temperature INPs depends on secondary ice production processes, among the least
158 understood areas of cloud microphysics due to observational challenges (Field, et al., 2017).

159 Satellites play a crucial role in understanding ACI. However, satellite instruments have
160 difficulty constraining ACI directly due to limitations on the data available (e.g. retrievals of
161 aerosols and clouds have been mutually exclusive). While comparisons with aircraft data have
162 shown that many cloud microphysical properties can be well retrieved in stratocumulus clouds
163 (Gryspeerd 2022), the retrievals are less reliable in broken cloud regimes, where even
164 retrievals of straightforward properties (e.g. cloud fraction) can be uncertain (Rosenfeld et al.,
165 2023). This is a particular issue for studies of cloud adjustments, which may be stronger in
166 regions of broken clouds where the cloud fraction can be modified (Chen et al., 2023).

167 For projecting future climate change, Earth System Models (ESMs) are still the only
168 viable tools available to the community. However, clouds are heavily parametrized in ESMs, and
169 their simulated ERF_{aci} strongly depends on the details of the parametrizations. Past studies are
170 heavily biased toward shallow liquid clouds to the detriment of mixed-phase clouds, deep
171 convective clouds, and ice clouds. This bias happened despite evidence that all types of clouds
172 potentially contribute to ERF_{aci}, while several cloud types such as convective clouds are poorly
173 or not at all treated in ESMs. Prominent issues, such as the Southern-Ocean shortwave
174 radiation bias (Kay et al., 2016; Fiddes et al., 2022) clearly show that the current representation
175 of aerosol and dynamics in model simulations is still far away from being able to accurately
176 capture regional differences, even on large oceanic scales. The simulation of ice crystal
177 concentrations in ESMs is affected by the representation of INP concentrations and their
178 uncertainties, which leads to discrepancies in the modeled top-of-atmosphere radiative flux
179 and, thereby, in the overall climate sensitivity of the models to greenhouse gases (Vergara-
180 Temprado et al., 2018).

181 Aerosol effects on deep convective clouds influence precipitation and extreme events (Li
182 et al., 2017; Navarro et al., 2017; Fan & Li, 2022), yet these remain difficult to model due to
183 coarse spatial resolution. Resolving mesoscale storms and extreme rainfall requires km-scale
184 resolutions (Fosser et al., 2024), which are not feasible for routine long-term climate modeling
185 (Schär et al., 2020). Current high-resolution climate ensembles and CORDEX models lack
186 prognostic ACI (Haarsma et al., 2016), limiting their ability to investigate precipitation effects.

187 In summary, constraining aerosol-cloud interactions remains a significant challenge in
188 climate science. ACI dominates the remaining uncertainty in human-induced warming over the
189 industrial era, and induces major uncertainties also for precipitation, extreme events and other
190 weather and climate factors. These uncertainties have strong implications for policymakers,

191 limiting the robust assessment of the impacts of potential strategies to mitigate and adapt to
192 climate change, which can ultimately evolve into policy.

193 **2 Where ACI uncertainties are currently barriers to good policy advice**

194 Understanding ACI, and constraining their influence on anthropogenic climate change,
195 are in themselves key scientific challenges. However, given the rapid rate of global warming and
196 the urgency of implementing emissions mitigation and adaptation measures, the remaining
197 large uncertainties associated with this set of processes are also hindrances for delivering solid
198 and quantitative knowledge to policy makers and stakeholders. Critically the limitations posed
199 by ACI may not even be fully acknowledged, possibly leading to overreliance on some
200 conclusions. In other cases, the possibilities or explanations that lie in ACI may not be fully
201 taken into consideration, because they are regarded as too uncertain. In this section, we outline
202 some of these situations.

203 2.1. Explaining recent global surface temperature trends and records

204 An acceleration in energy accumulation in the global ocean since the 1990s has been
205 documented by a range of studies (Cheng et al., 2024). Recently, an uptick has also been seen in
206 the global top-of-atmosphere energy imbalance (Loeb et al., 2024), in the overall heating of the
207 Earth System (Minière et al., 2023), and in global mean surface warming (Forster et al., 2025).
208 The increase in energy imbalance over recent decades has been attributed partly to a global
209 reduction in anthropogenic aerosol emissions (Hodnebrog et al., 2024). Notably, the year 2023
210 became the warmest on record, by a margin that surprised many. Throughout the year, record
211 ocean surface temperatures were observed in multiple basins, including in the Central and East
212 Pacific, where an El Nino event unfolded (Samset et al., 2024). Beyond the influence of ocean
213 variability, however, several aerosol related mechanisms have been proposed. These include
214 the strong, rapid and sustained reductions in Chinese SO₂ emissions (Samset et al., 2025), the
215 2020 International Maritime Organization regulations reducing SO₂ emissions from
216 intercontinental shipping (Yuan et al., 2022; Diamond, 2023), and the low amounts of Saharan
217 dust. Residual effects from the stratospheric water vapor injected by the January 2022 Hunga
218 Tonga volcanic eruption has also been suggested as a contributing factor (Schoeberl et al.,
219 2024).

220 While upcoming research will likely constrain the influences of each of these factors on
221 recent temperature trends, ACI uncertainty remains a limiting factor. As an example, recent
222 changes in shipping SO₂ emissions force the climate directly via sulfate aerosols, and indirectly
223 via ship tracks, which occur when ship-emitted aerosols interact with low clouds. The 2020
224 International Maritime Organization fuel regulations contributed to reducing ship-track
225 frequency to its lowest level in recent decades (Yuan et al., 2022). However, the influence of
226 this change on the global and regional radiative balance or surface temperatures, is highly
227 uncertain due to large internal variability (Watson-Parris et al., 2024).

228 Similarly, the influence of recent strong East Asian SO₂ emission reductions, where the
229 observational evidence is clear (Xiang et al., 2023) and modeling estimates of the climate

230 influences of regional aerosol emissions exist (Gao et al., 2023; Samset et al., 2025), the ACI
231 uncertainties are generally acknowledged as limiting factors. Notably, the potential for a
232 saturation of the ACI with high aerosol loadings is important, as is the heterogeneous dynamical
233 response of the climate system to regional forcing (Jia & Quaas, 2023). In combination, they
234 mean that even for a known change in global aerosol loading from East Asian sulfur emissions,
235 the total, realized local radiative forcing is poorly constrained, as are the subsequent influences
236 on local and remote surface temperature.

237 However, taken together with the earlier rise in anthropogenic aerosol emissions in East
238 and South Asia, since around 1980, the industrialization and air quality policies in China and
239 neighboring countries represents an ideal, if unintended, testbed for hypotheses concerning
240 the broader impacts of anthropogenic activities on climate changes. As discussed below, this
241 opportunity should be taken by the observational and modelling communities, as well as
242 developers of climate model emulators and impact assessment frameworks (Persad et al.
243 2023).

244 2.2. Constraining the equilibrium climate sensitivity and transient climate response.

245 The most recent assessment of equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS), in the IPCC AR6
246 (Forster et al., 2021) was based on multiple lines of evidence; paleoclimate, feedback process
247 understanding, emergent constraints, and historical observational record. Initially, aerosol ERF,
248 and hence ACI, was only considered to be directly and strongly relevant for the last of these,
249 the observational record. However, for transient climate response (TCR), the historical
250 observational record is a more central line of evidence, and therefore aerosol ERF also becomes
251 much more influential. Recent literature indicates that the overall aerosol forcing may be
252 stronger than previously thought (Julsrud et al., 2022), partly due to not accounting for the
253 coupling between clouds and the boundary layer (Su et al., 2024). Apart from forcing, the
254 natural aerosols, and their changing profiles from the effects of climate change, modulate
255 clouds and precipitation. This means that the climate sensitivity is also shifting and ACI plays a
256 critical role that goes beyond the established concept of "anthropogenic aerosol forcing"
257 (Gettelman et al., 2016). Estimates of ECS and TCR are influenced by uncertainties in climate
258 effects of aerosols, which are - in turn - dominated by ACI uncertainties. Interestingly, recent
259 studies that use aerosol/cloud-observations in combination with ESMs give higher ECS/TCR
260 than the central estimate in the IPCC AR6 assessment (Forster et al., 2021), while methods
261 utilizing rates and/or patterns of warming in combination with ESMs give central ECS/TCR
262 estimates close to, or lower than, the IPCC AR6 assessment (Ricard et al., 2024) - but also do
263 not rule out the higher values. Clearly, further work is required to resolve these apparent
264 discrepancies in these different lines of evidence. Better constraints on ACI is a key component
265 in this work, as it represents a dominating source of uncertainty for a core constraint on ECS
266 and TCR.

267 2.3. Pinning down the remaining carbon budget.

268 Estimates of the amount of carbon we may still emit while staying below 1.5°C, or any
269 other strong mitigation target, are heavily influenced by the uncertainty in non-CO2 forcing

270 (Forster et al., 2021). The uncertainty in non-CO₂ ERF is, in turn, dominated by the uncertainty
271 in ACI (Forster et al., 2021). Uncertainty in ERF_{aci} relevant for carbon budgets includes both the
272 geophysical uncertainty of how strong the present day ACI is (how much warming has been
273 offset), and scenario uncertainty in how emissions trends will develop in the coming years. The
274 majority of the more than 1000 emissions scenarios produced by integrated assessment models
275 that are assessed by the IPCC show a decline in aerosol emissions in the coming decades (Riahi
276 et al., 2022), due to an expected strengthening of clean air policies around the world (Rao et al.,
277 2017), with large uncertainty in future natural emissions in a warming world. Rapid reductions
278 in aerosols remove their temporary cooling, causing an earlier and higher peak warming that
279 can influence the level and duration of any temperature overshoot of 1.5°C even if levels later
280 fall below Paris targets. This is relevant, since climate risks depend on peak as well as long-term
281 warming (Schleussner et al. 2024). Slower phase-outs delay this unmasking but prolong
282 pollution. Because aerosols mainly affect near-term forcing, their earlier reduction tightens the
283 remaining carbon budget—by roughly 100–200 Gt CO₂—making early, deep greenhouse-gas
284 cuts essential to limit both overshoot and peak warming (IPCC, 2021). This gradual reduction in
285 net cooling influence reduces the available space for CO₂ emissions and hence limits the
286 remaining carbon budget (Shindell & Smith, 2019; Stjern et al., 2023). Revisions to how ERF_{aci}
287 and its uncertainty is assessed can therefore have significant impacts on the 1.5°C carbon
288 budget, given the small amount of headroom left until this limit is exceeded (Lamboll et al.,
289 2023; Forster et al., 2025). More generally, ACI is a strong determinant of the expected
290 warming from any emissions pathway and can make the difference to whether a mitigation
291 scenario is consistent with Paris Agreement temperature goals or not (Watson-Parris & Smith,
292 2022).

293 2.4. Projecting regional precipitation change and likelihood of extreme events

294 Understanding the rates and magnitudes of changes in precipitation and extreme
295 weather events are among the most crucial topics for adaptation strategies. Here, ACI comes in
296 because aerosols affect atmospheric radiation via different physical mechanisms to greenhouse
297 gases, notably through changing clouds, and through scattering and absorbing shortwave
298 radiation. Broad consensus and strong theoretical evidence exist that ACI is a contributing
299 driver of global precipitation changes, mediated via affecting atmospheric energetics and
300 surface evaporation. ACI is also causing well-documented shifts of large-scale precipitation
301 patterns, such as the intertropical convergence zone. The extent of aerosol effects on
302 precipitation at smaller scales is however less clear. Aerosol perturbations microphysically
303 increase cloud droplet numbers and decrease droplet sizes, thereby slowing precipitation
304 formation, however the overall aerosol effect on precipitation across scales remains highly
305 uncertain (Stier et al. 2024). Therefore, a better understanding of ACI and their representation
306 in climate models can lead to more robust science-based policy.

307 Aerosol forcing is much more localized than greenhouse gas forcing, has stronger
308 seasonal and diurnal variations, and influences regions far from the emission sources via
309 tropical (Dong et al., 2014) and midlatitude (Wilcox et al., 2019) teleconnections. Several
310 studies have shown that the overall influence of aerosols on precipitation and extreme event

311 rates is different to greenhouse gases (Stier et al., 2024). A recent review (Wang et al., 2022)
312 also explored the specific influence of aerosols on meteorological extremes, noting the specific
313 mechanisms affecting temperature, winds, humidity, turbulence and boundary layer conditions,
314 and subsequent extreme conditions. Black carbon, which imposes strong heating aloft through
315 shortwave absorption, is expected to have an outsized effect on precipitation, both directly,
316 and indirectly via modifying clouds (ACI) (Samset et al., 2024). Additionally, studies
317 demonstrate aerosol influences on monsoons, tropical cyclones, extreme heat waves,
318 thunderstorms and more (Rosenfeld et al., 2007; Persad et al., 2023), including efforts
319 exploiting the unintended experiment presented by the recent decadal scale changes in East
320 Asian aerosol emissions (Li et al., 2016, 2019). These regional impacts also have important
321 implications on policy. Models that represent convection and cloud formation in any detail
322 (convection resolving models, regional climate models) generally do not yet include aerosols
323 treatment, or aerosol-cloud interactions, and those that have ACI included do not agree on the
324 strength and sign of their effect (Marinescu et al., 2021).

325 In summary, the current uncertainty in ACI is hampering proper projections of both the
326 frequency of extremes under present and future conditions, and the properties of individual
327 events or compounds of multiple extremes.

328 2.5 Providing advice on the efficiency and side effects of solar radiation modification

329 Some types of solar radiation modification, notably cloud brightening and cirrus cloud
330 thinning, rely on aerosol induced modification of cloud properties. It is noted that cloud
331 brightening refers to both land and ocean - while often marine cloud brightening is considered
332 since such clouds are more susceptible to aerosol perturbations, there may be reasons to focus
333 on continental clouds as well (Quaas et al. 2016). We also note that some studies consider
334 mixed-phase clouds in solar radiation modification schemes as well (Villanueva et al., 2022).
335 Please note the inconsistency in the term “solar radiation modification” for cirrus and mixed-
336 phase cloud thinning which in fact target mainly terrestrial radiation. ACI uncertainties
337 therefore influence our ability to constrain the climate responses both directly, and indirectly,
338 by also limiting our ability to interpret natural analogues such as volcanic eruptions. While
339 climate models indicate that reducing global-mean temperatures via solar radiation
340 modification techniques is feasible in principle, a wide range of side effects are to be expected,
341 differing between the type of implementation (Stjern et al., 2018). Cloud brightening and cirrus
342 and mixed-phase cloud thinning technologies are of interest since in principle they can be
343 applied at a scale limited in space and time (Gruber et al., 2019; Villanueva et al., 2022;
344 Hernandez-Jaramillo et al., 2025), e.g. targeting only specific regions and/or targeting
345 mitigation of specific climate extremes such as heatwaves (Afroz et al., 2023). However, it is
346 unclear to which extent it is feasible to indeed limit effects, and modeling tools are not yet
347 mature for reliable anticipation and attribution of the seeding outcomes (Quaas et al., 2016).
348 Here, lack of ACI implementation and physical processes at high resolution is a critical
349 shortcoming. Recently, marine cloud brightening has been considered to be effective based on
350 the responses of cloud properties to volcanic eruptions (Chen et al., 2024). However, since
351 cloud brightening is proposed to be done using spraying of sea salt, processes related to

352 spraying (e.g., evaporation of water) will have implications on cloud formation (Feingold et al.,
353 2024) and is hence also limited by poor constraints on ACI. Better understanding and
354 representation of ACI leads to better assessment of climate impacts of aerosol-based SRMs, as
355 well as their possible adverse impacts on circulation and ecosystems, leading to more robust
356 policy advice on the mitigation of climate change.

357 2.6. Quantifying the link between extreme weather events, air quality and global health
358 issues

359 A well-known tradeoff in climate and air quality policy is that while reducing aerosol
360 emissions leads to clear benefits for air quality and human and ecosystem health (Im et al.,
361 2023; Wei et al., 2023), it also leads to a reduction in their masking of the warming induced by
362 greenhouse gases (Yuan et al., 2024). Recent studies estimate that without this masking, global
363 temperatures would already be close to 2°C above pre-industrial levels, rather than the ~1.4°C
364 currently observed (Hausfather, 2025). This “unmasking” effect has contributed approximately
365 0.14°C of the ~0.5°C warming since 2007, with notable contributions from declining sulphur
366 emissions in China (Samset et al., 2025) and maritime fuel regulations. The sulfur content
367 regulation is a typical example of the trade-off between air quality and climate policy trade-offs.
368 While no policy advocates weakening air quality standards to mitigate warming, the interplay
369 between aerosol reductions, climate extremes, and health impacts must be better understood.
370 Reductions in aerosols can exacerbate extreme weather events—such as heatwaves, floods,
371 and droughts—by accelerating warming and altering precipitation patterns (Persad et al., 2022;
372 Akinyoola et al., 2024). These events pose direct and indirect health risks, including respiratory
373 and cardiovascular stress and mortality. A major barrier to quantifying these risks is the regional
374 dependency of aerosols and their interactions with clouds and their sensitivity to cloud-surface
375 coupling, diurnal cycles, and aerosol composition (Herbert et al., 2025; Su et al., 2024). The
376 clouds also impact the incoming radiation, which drives formation of certain atmospheric
377 species like O₃, which impact air quality (Im et al., 2022), and therefore human health (Im et al.,
378 2023), as well as ecosystems (Emberson, 2020). To move forward, it is essential to adopt a
379 holistic approach to understanding aerosol and cloud life cycles across different regimes. Such
380 efforts are critical not only for improving climate projections but also for developing robust risk
381 assessments and early warning systems that can inform adaptation strategies under varying
382 aerosol emission futures. 2.1 A descriptive heading about methods

383 **3 Next Steps for Advancing Aerosol-Cloud Interaction Research**

384 Having highlighted the remaining knowledge gaps in our understanding of how ACI
385 influences the current and future changes to the global climate, and the limitations they pose
386 for the ability of the scientific community to deliver actionable policy advice, the next step is to
387 outline a plan for closing the knowledge gaps in a timely manner. There are emerging
388 opportunities in observations, modelling, analysis and computing techniques, and community
389 efforts, that open for rapid progress if properly leveraged. These opportunities are summarized

390 in Table 1, along with their timelines of when concrete results can be achieved in immediate,
391 short (1-5 years), mid (5-10 years), and longer (10-20 years) terms.

392 3.1. Improving Satellite Data and Retrieval Accuracy

393 Satellite data are essential for providing global-scale insights into ACI, but are limited
394 with respect to resolution, sensitivity and available observables. This together with limitations
395 in current retrieval methods leads to difficulties in accurately determining cloud micro- and
396 macrophysical properties such as droplet number concentration, cloud-top phase, liquid water
397 path and cloud fraction, particularly in broken cloud regimes. Furthermore, retrievals of cloud
398 condensation nuclei (CCN) concentrations are hampered by lack of information content or
399 retrieval biases (Hasekamp et al. 2019a). These uncertainties in satellite-based retrievals hinder
400 our understanding of ACI and its role in climate change. A holistic view of different
401 measurement techniques and platforms is therefore essential to transfer knowledge gained on
402 smaller scales (cloud to regional scale) to the larger scale (continental to global scale), and to
403 define observables serving as indicators for different processes. Therefore, the next steps
404 should focus on:

405 *Reassessing satellite constraints:* New advancements in satellite technology necessitate
406 revisiting existing retrieval algorithms. Much of the current understanding of aerosol impacts
407 on clouds is based on satellite retrievals of cloud properties like droplet concentration and
408 liquid water path and their relationships. However, recent studies reveal that these cloud
409 retrievals often carry significant biases due to assumptions made in the retrieval process (Arola
410 et al., 2022), as in the case of cloud fraction in broken cloud regimes (Rosenfeld et al., 2023).
411 Furthermore, retrieved aerosol products, such as spectral aerosol optical depth, are shown to
412 be biased or poor proxies for CCN (Hasekamp et al. 2019a). The cloud and aerosol microphysical
413 retrieval schemes should be improved by refining the algorithms based on updated scattering
414 models (Gasteiger & Wiegner, 2018) and by adding missing information from remote sensing
415 (i.e. polarization, fluorescence: Grosvenor et al. 2018; Quaas et al. 2020; Dubovik et al., 2021,
416 Patel et al. 2024; Lv et al. 2018). Updating these constraints by incorporating newer retrieval
417 techniques will provide more reliable global estimates of ACI and reduce uncertainties in
418 estimating the ERF_{aci} .

419 *Multi-instrument synergy:* The deep synergy approaches exploring complementarity of multi-
420 instrument observations is another promising direction for improving accuracy of remote
421 sensing products needed for ACI studies (Dubovik et al., 2021). Indeed, no single sensor
422 provides comprehensive information about aerosol and cloud properties, especially in a
423 complex environment. Therefore, there is always a need to inject the missing information from
424 complementary observations, modeling or other sources of knowledge. Specifically, ACI
425 investigations will clearly benefit from synergy of passive imagery with active vertical profiling
426 (Ewald et al., 2021) of the atmosphere performed at different spectral ranges and at different
427 time or spatial scales. In addition, once the instruments have been deployed, the quality of
428 measurements cannot be radically improved, while the processing algorithms remain under
429 constant improvement and the final product can be notably improved by fusion of information

430 from the datasets based on the observations of different sensitivities. Furthermore, the
431 combination of different techniques (e.g. in-situ and remote sensing) allows us to transfer
432 information about changes in the aerosol and cloud microphysical properties to observables in
433 remote sensing measurements, which is essential to observe specific processes from space.
434 Similarly, combining satellite observations with sub-orbital measurements and chemical
435 transport model results is expected to be increasingly utilized for ACI analysis.

436 *Combining ground-based and aircraft measurements, and satellite remote sensing:* Although
437 satellite observations provide broad global coverage, they usually lack the detailed resolution
438 and precision of ground-based and aircraft remote sensing and in-situ measurements. Quality-
439 assured suborbital measurements from ground and air are needed to validate the satellite
440 products, improve the retrieval algorithms and advance the retrieved information by utilizing
441 synergies from ground/air/space. Ground-based remote sensing measurements provide long-
442 term, real-time, high-quality data on aerosol optical properties, which can be used to validate
443 and refine satellite retrievals (Wandinger et al., 2010; Kanitz et al., 2014; Papagiannopoulos et
444 al., 2016). Airborne measurements with similar instrumentation but higher precision, sensitivity
445 and resolution allow for direct comparisons for validation, verification and algorithm test,
446 assuring sufficient quality of satellite measurements for ACI studies. High resolution airborne
447 measurements during dedicated campaigns are furthermore crucial to increase our knowledge
448 on ACI processes but are limited in time and space. It is thus essential to combine these
449 missions with long-term ground-based and satellite measurements to transfer this knowledge
450 to a long-term and global scale. Combination of different measurement techniques are the
451 backbone in defining observables retrieved from long-term and satellite missions that lead as
452 indicators for ACI processes. European Research Infrastructures such as ACTRIS (Laj et al., 2024)
453 and US facilities such as ARM are of paramount importance, to provide the quality assured
454 aerosol and cloud remote sensing and in-situ data from ground, while other infrastructures (e.g.
455 IAGOS) can add airborne information from commercial aircraft worldwide (Thouret et al.,
456 2022). In addition, dedicated field and flight experiments provide deep insights in ACI processes
457 on a cloud to regional scale. Ground-based remote sensing techniques, such as lidar and radar,
458 complemented by in-situ aerosol and cloud microphysical measurements at high-altitude sites,
459 offer the ability to observe cloud properties and aerosol profiles in three dimensions, providing
460 a more comprehensive view of ACI processes (Wieder et al., 2022). Tailored experimental
461 campaigns combining ground and airborne datasets during satellite overpasses are vital for
462 addressing specific ACI objectives, by combining aircraft in-situ, profiling and radiation
463 measurements, and ground-based profiling from remote sensing techniques towards depicting
464 a complete picture of ACI, helping to generalize detailed, localized measurements to the global
465 scale. Integrating satellite, aircraft and ground-based data will enable more accurate retrievals
466 of cloud properties in challenging conditions, such as regions with complex cloud dynamics. In
467 addition, automations on adaptive cloud monitoring with scanning cloud radars and Doppler
468 lidars will allow documenting the 3-D and 4-D cloud evolution, tracking of cloud elements to
469 provide statistical representations of the evolution of the cloud structure and precipitation

470 (Mason et al., 2023), and to improve retrievals of cloud microphysical properties (Heske et al.,
471 2025).

472 *Combining observations and models within data assimilation systems:* Both traditional
473 variational or ensemble-based and more recently ML-methods offer an ideal framework to
474 combine observations and models to learn about ACI processes. In the data assimilation
475 framework, it is possible to estimate atmospheric variables and model parameters that might
476 be poorly observed (Scheck et al., 2020). For example, satellite data can be leveraged for global
477 estimates of CCN by using the data assimilation as a sophisticated retrieval (Fielding &
478 Janiskova, 2020; Janiskova & Fielding, 2020). The advantage of doing that is that dynamical,
479 thermodynamical, and microphysical cloud and aerosol properties need to be consistent within
480 the chosen assimilation system. Additionally, the data assimilation system can also exploit
481 synergies between different observations (ground-based, space-borne, etc.), offering a unified
482 framework for the treatment of model and observations.

483 3.2. Leveraging Upcoming Satellite Missions for ACI Insights

484 Several new satellite missions, such as ESA EarthCARE (Wehr et al., 2023), NASA PACE
485 (Werdell et al., 2019), both launched in 2024, and ESA/EUMETSAT 3MI (Fougnie et al., 2018) are
486 expected to provide groundbreaking data on ACI. These missions offer new opportunities to
487 reduce uncertainties and improve constraints on climate models. Researchers should focus on
488 maximizing the potential of these missions by integrating their data with existing observational
489 and modeling frameworks, and to link them to ongoing or completed satellite missions e.g.
490 NASA's CALIPSO (Winker et al., 2010) and Cloudsat (Stephens et al., 2008) as well as their
491 combined exploitation (Stephens et al., 2018). Key priorities include:

492 *Maximizing data from EarthCARE and PACE:* The EarthCARE satellite provides unprecedented
493 high-resolved correlative observations of aerosol, clouds, and radiation from space (Wehr et al.,
494 2023). Its high-spectral-resolution lidar ATLID delivers, for the first time, global data sets of
495 directly measured extinction profiles and thus invaluable information on aerosol properties at
496 the altitudes where clouds reside and ACI takes place. Independent measurements of particle
497 extinction-to-backscatter and depolarization ratios with ATLID allow for a dedicated aerosol
498 classification (Wandinger et al., 2023), which is the precondition for CCN and INP concentration
499 retrievals based on optical-to-microphysical conversion techniques (Ansmann et al., 2019).

500 The cloud-profiling radar CPR with its novel Doppler capability contributes information
501 on convective motions as well as ice precipitation and rainfall speeds, leading to improved
502 drizzle, rainfall and snowfall rates. Synergistic retrieval products based on multi-instrument
503 data allow direct access to EarthCARE's combined aerosol, cloud, and precipitation information
504 (Mason et al., 2023). Similarly, PACE mission delivers advanced polarimetric measurements of
505 aerosol and cloud properties, allowing for unprecedented retrievals of cloud droplet size
506 distributions and concentrations (Werdell et al., 2019). Climate models should be constrained
507 with these datasets, once they are calibrated and validated (Cal/Val) against other independent

508 measurements, to improve the accuracy of ACI simulations and reduce uncertainties in cloud
509 radiative forcing.

510 *Utilizing new polarimetric instruments:* Instruments like HARP-2 and SPEXone on PACE are
511 designed to measure the particle size distribution PSD of liquid clouds using polarimetric
512 techniques. These instruments provide a more accurate calibration error-free retrieval of cloud
513 droplet sizes compared to traditional bi-spectral retrievals, particularly in regions with
514 inhomogeneous cloud structures (Alexandrov et al., 2012). Combining these observations with
515 data from EarthCARE's high-spectral-resolution lidar will offer a powerful tool for constraining
516 cloud microphysical properties and understanding aerosol-induced cloud adjustments. Aerosol
517 retrievals from accurate Multi-Angle Polarimeter (MAP) measurements have the capability to
518 provide aerosol size distribution, column-integrated number concentration, and composition
519 (Dubovik et al., 2019). These properties determine the suitability of aerosols to act as CCN and
520 therefore can be used to derive CCN proxies which are more suited to quantify ACI than proxies
521 based on aerosol optical properties (Hasekamp et al., 2019a). The SPEXone instrument on PACE
522 (Hasekamp et al., 2019b) is designed to provide such retrievals also over land and for cleaner
523 conditions (e.g. over oceans), which are of high importance for ACI (Gryspeerd et al., 2023).

524 *Exploiting temporal information to constrain ACI:* Clouds and cloud adjustment to aerosol are
525 inherently time-dependent (Li & Groß, 2022) - failing to consider this can lead to large biases in
526 estimates of ACI from natural experiments such as ship tracks (Glassmeier et al., 2021) or to
527 investigate impacts of anthropogenic aerosols, e.g. the impact of aviation induced aerosols on
528 ice clouds. Building on the success of SEVIRI for cloud retrievals, the new generation of
529 geostationary satellites (GOES, MTG-I) will provide a highly detailed picture of cloud temporal
530 evolution at scales previously only accessible to snapshot imagery from polar-orbiting
531 instruments. Coupled to new methods to characterize cloud development and the response to
532 aerosol perturbations (Gryspeerd et al., 2021), this will move constraints on ACI towards the
533 process timescales essential for constraining global model behavior and parameterizations.

534 *Long-term satellite monitoring through METOP-SG and CO2M Missions:* The METOP-SG and
535 CO2M missions, scheduled for launch later this decade, will provide long-term monitoring of
536 aerosol and cloud properties over multiple decades (Dubovik et al., 2019). The METOP-SG
537 mission, developed jointly by ESA and EUMETSAT, is designed to extend and enhance the
538 capabilities of the first-generation METOP satellites, which have been operational since 2006.
539 METOP-SG will ensure continuity of polar-orbiting meteorological observations for weather
540 forecasting and climate monitoring over the next two decades. Unlike its predecessor, METOP-
541 SG consists of instruments to observe atmospheric temperature, humidity, aerosols, cloud
542 properties, and trace gases with significantly improved spatial resolution and accuracy. This
543 continuity is essential for maintaining long-term climate records and detecting subtle trends in
544 atmospheric composition and aerosol-cloud interactions (ACI).

545 The CO2M mission, part of the Copernicus Sentinel Expansion program, represents a
546 new observational initiative focused specifically on monitoring anthropogenic greenhouse gas
547 emissions, particularly carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). CO2M

548 will deploy a constellation of three satellites equipped with advanced instruments, including
549 the Integrated CO₂ and NO₂ Imaging Spectrometer (CO2I), a Multi-Angular Polarimeter (MAP),
550 and a Cloud Imager (CLIM). These instruments will enable high-resolution measurements of
551 greenhouse gases and aerosols, facilitating the quantification and verification of human-
552 induced emissions at regional and national scales. This mission is not a continuation of previous
553 satellite programs but rather a strategic expansion aimed at supporting climate policy and
554 emission reduction efforts under frameworks like the Paris Agreement.

555 In summary, these missions will be particularly valuable for detecting trends in aerosol
556 emissions and their impacts on cloud systems. The continuity of these datasets will be critical
557 for understanding how ACI evolves in response to changes in both natural and anthropogenic
558 aerosol emissions.

559 3.3. Enhancing observational campaigns and long-term ground-based measurements

560 Ground-based observations, eventually combined with aircraft data, provide critical
561 information that satellite data alone cannot capture, greatly supporting ACI processes
562 understanding (Virtanen et al., 2025). The wealth of synergies which arise from multi-sensor
563 deployments is essential for improving our understanding of aerosol-cloud interactions and
564 validating satellite observations. Observational campaigns, such as those involving ground-
565 based remote sensing networks, must be expanded to fill key data gaps. The next steps in this
566 area include:

567 *Expanding ground-based long-term vertical profile measurements:* Accurate monitoring of
568 aerosol and clouds requires advanced vertical profiling techniques. Synergies, both by means of
569 technical aspects as well as retrieval-wise, provide a wealth of opportunities for extended
570 approaches. Combined cloud radar and multi-field-of view lidar observations enable the
571 characterization of liquid and ice cloud microphysical properties simultaneously (Jimenez et al.,
572 2025). Fixed-altitude in-situ or column-integrated observations can be scaled to the vertical
573 dimension by calibration against profiling remote sensing measurements as it is done in lidar-
574 based INP and CCN retrievals (Mamouri & Ansmann, 2016) or multi-instrument mixed-phase
575 cloud retrievals (Pasquier et al., 2022). Scanning cloud Doppler radars and lidars are in addition
576 key for retrieving further insights into aerosol and cloud processes. Scanning polarimetry
577 complements the classification of detected targets (Myagkov et al., 2016; Tैसेire et al., 2024)
578 while Doppler-velocity-resolved observations provide insights into the co-located presence of
579 targets in a cloud volume including the presence of secondary ice formation or liquid droplets in
580 deep mixed-phase clouds (Schimmel et al., 2022; Billault-Roux et al., 2023; Vogl et al., 2024).
581 Scanning observations in general can document cloud evolution in three and four dimensions
582 and are thus key technologies for understanding aerosol impacts on cloud formation and
583 dissipation. These tools can track the time-dependent responses of clouds to aerosol
584 perturbations (Lopatin et al., 2021). For instance, cloud adjustments to aerosol perturbations,
585 including changes in cloud fraction and liquid water content in globally frequently occurring
586 situations of broken clouds will become trackable using scanning observations for following the

587 evolution of a targeted air mass. By automating the collection of vertical profiles, the cloud life
588 cycle and the processes that drive aerosol-induced cloud adjustments can be better captured.

589 *Deploying drones and balloons for in-situ profiling:* In addition to ground-based instruments,
590 drones and tethered balloons equipped with aerosol and cloud sensors are emerging as
591 valuable tools for capturing detailed in-situ profiles of CCN and INPs. These platforms allow for
592 high-resolution measurements directly within clouds (Henneberger et al., 2023), providing data
593 that is otherwise challenging to obtain with conventional aircraft. In-situ measurements from
594 these and piloted aircraft are crucial for understanding cloud formation mechanisms, aerosol
595 activation processes, ice nucleation (Miller et al., 2025) and the vertical structure of clouds, as
596 well as for obtaining detailed aerosol microphysical and chemical properties, such as particle
597 hygroscopicity, mass extinction efficiency, and CCN spectrum, that are needed to quantify ACI
598 processes but are currently lacking (Kahn et al., 2017).

599 3.4. Refining climate models to accurately simulate ACI

600 Climate models are the primary tools for predicting and projecting the future climate
601 and how ACI will influence the Earth's radiative budget and broader climate in the future.
602 However, these models are often limited by their coarse resolution and the incomplete
603 representation of aerosol-cloud processes. Addressing these limitations will require significant
604 improvements in model resolution, parameterization, and evaluation techniques. The next
605 steps include:

606 *Developing aerosol-aware, high-resolution models:* Current global climate models and regional
607 climate models typically run at resolutions that are too coarse to resolve cloud-scale processes.
608 This limits the ability of models to accurately simulate extreme weather events and the
609 influence of aerosols on cloud dynamics. Recent advances in high-resolution climate modeling,
610 such as kilometer-scale models, offer the potential to resolve cloud dynamics more explicitly,
611 improving the representation of ACI. These high-resolution models can simulate convection
612 directly, providing more realistic simulations of mesoscale convective systems and extreme
613 precipitation events (Fosser et al., 2024). Integrating interactive aerosols into these models will
614 provide the first consistent assessments of ACI across different cloud types, although it is
615 unclear what level of complexity is required to simulate ACI realistically in high-resolution
616 models. The challenge in coupling ACI processes to high-resolution models will be the
617 computational cost and the amount of data that will require simplification of aerosol-cloud
618 modules. Machine learning will facilitate computational efficiency to account for complex ACI
619 processes in climate models, e.g. through use of emulators that can replace some microphysical
620 models or processes such as precipitation formation or vertical velocities (e.g. Yuval &
621 O’Gorman, 2020; Gettelman et al., 2021; Ahola et al., 2022; Omanovic et al., 2025). They may
622 also facilitate incorporation of previously computationally too demanding complexity, such as
623 superdroplet parameterizations, through emulation (Sharma and Greenberg, 2025).

624 *Process-based model evaluation:* Process-based model evaluation focuses on comparing
625 modeled processes with observed processes rather than simply comparing bulk quantities. This
626 approach allows for a more detailed understanding of how well models capture the physical

627 processes and feedbacks underlying ACI (Omanovic et al., 2025). By integrating long-term
628 observational data with satellite and in-situ measurements, process-based evaluations can
629 provide more robust constraints on model performance (Blichner et al., 2024; Virtanen et al.,
630 2025). These evaluations are particularly valuable for understanding the complex interactions
631 between aerosols, cloud microphysics, and atmospheric dynamics.

632 *Improving representations of aerosol size distributions, composition, and updrafts:* The ability of
633 aerosols to influence cloud properties depends largely on aerosol size distribution and
634 composition, and the strength of updrafts in the cloud. Current models often struggle to
635 represent these factors sufficiently, leading to large uncertainties in estimates of cloud droplet
636 number concentration and cloud albedo (Soponaro et al., 2020; Motos et al., 2023).
637 Improvements in the representation of aerosol size distributions, aerosol composition,
638 hygroscopicity, and updraft velocities are urgently needed to better capture the sensitivity of
639 cloud properties to aerosols (e.g. Twomey effect, ice crystal formation, precipitation formation)
640 (Burgos et al., 2020; Virtanen et al., 2025; Zheng et al., 2015, 2016, 2021). Global observations
641 of updraft velocities at cloud base, where aerosol activation occurs, will be critical for improving
642 model accuracy. While high-resolution climate models can better capture small-scale processes,
643 the description of sub-grid scale processes such as cloud activation updrafts will remain a
644 challenge. Finally, natural aerosols, such as dust and biological particles, which contribute to
645 INPs and therefore ice production, should be included in models (Fiedler et al., 2024; Gao et al.,
646 2024; Chatziparaschos et al., 2025).

647 3.5. Focusing on natural aerosols in a post-fossil regime and warming world

648 As the world transitions to cleaner energy sources, natural aerosols such as dust, sea
649 salt, biogenic particles, and biomass burning aerosols will become increasingly important for
650 determining future climate. In addition, climate change and human activity can lead to changes
651 in emission strengths and locations, as well as in atmospheric processes associated with natural
652 aerosols (Schmale et al., 2021; Dall'Osto et al., 2018). Understanding these dynamic natural
653 aerosol sources and their interactions with clouds is essential for future climate projections.
654 Future research must prioritize:

655 *Improving understanding and modelling of natural aerosol emissions:* Natural aerosols,
656 including sea salt, dust, fire, and biogenic aerosols from vegetation and the oceans, are
657 expected to play a more significant role in the climate system as anthropogenic aerosols
658 decrease (Toll et al., 2017). However, these sources remain poorly understood, with significant
659 uncertainties surrounding how their emissions will respond to climate change (Mahowald et al.,
660 2024; Kok et al., 2023, Gali et al., 2019; Pernov et al., 2024, 2025), adding to existing
661 uncertainties in ACI and other aerosol effects. To improve future projections, studies must
662 enhance baseline knowledge of natural aerosol emissions and their trends. Leveraging paleo
663 data for components like dust and wildfire emissions could improve model constraints and

664 sensitivity to climate and human impacts. Future studies must focus on improving the baseline
665 understanding of natural aerosol emissions and their potential future trends.

666 *Improving understanding of interactions within and between natural and post-fossil*
667 *anthropogenic aerosols:* Altered emissions shift the ionic balance in particles and as a result
668 their composition does not reflect directly the emission changes due to anthropogenic and
669 natural aerosol interactions. For example, it has been observed that with less availability of
670 sulfuric acid, due to cleaner air quality policies, the nitrate component in aerosols has
671 increased, even though nitrogen dioxide emissions have been reduced simultaneously (Sharma
672 et al., 2019). Another example is the enhanced presence of ammonium in particles, which
673 allows natural acids such as methanesulfonic acid to preferentially enter the particle phase,
674 while if ammonium were absent methanesulfonic acid would preferentially stay in the gas
675 phase (Dada et al., 2022). As both anthropogenic and natural particle and precursor emissions
676 change, we expect the composition of particles to change, however involving more complex
677 chemical and thermodynamic processes. These processes need to be observed, understood,
678 and modeling skill built.

679 *Investigating natural aerosol-cloud feedback:* Natural aerosols, such as dust, biomass-burning
680 and biogenic particles, can act as CCN and INPs, influencing cloud formation and radiative
681 forcing (Gao et al., 2024; Chatziparaschos et al., 2025; He et al., 2025). Research into how these
682 aerosols contribute to cloud reflectivity and feedback mechanisms will be critical for improving
683 estimates of cloud radiative forcing and constraining climate sensitivity (Yli-Juuti et al., 2021).
684 Similarly, the influence of some natural aerosol sources on cloud properties, such as blowing
685 snow in the polar regions, has only recently been addressed, because observations were not
686 available for a quantitative assessment (Gong et al., 2023). Studies should also explore how
687 changes in natural aerosol emissions due to climate change will affect cloud properties in
688 different regions, such as how changes in the biogeochemistry of the oceans or continental
689 vegetation will impact aerosol emissions and in turn may impact cloud properties in the
690 coupled climate system.

691 *Laboratory studies of cloud relevant properties for natural aerosol and cloud microphysical*
692 *processes:* The aging of natural aerosols will result in an evolution of their CCN and INP
693 properties, which carries important implications for the clouds and their impacts in future
694 climate. There is a need for focused laboratory experiments (NASEM, 2016) to study these
695 processes and their impact on cloud microphysics, leveraging existing infrastructures such as
696 the ACTRIS. There is also a need for focused laboratory studies to probe cloud microphysical
697 processes that are poorly understood (e.g. supersaturation distributions in warm and mixed
698 phase clouds, secondary ice production, secondary activation, collision-coalescence and
699 aggregation, aerosol scavenging in clouds). For these, established cloud chamber facilities such
700 as PI (University of Michigan) and AIDA (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology) should be leveraged
701 from. These experiments could form the basis for development of parameterizations that are
702 critical for describing missing knowledge and processes in models. Such experiments can be
703 deployed in the laboratory or under hybrid laboratory/field conditions and can provide targeted

704 insight into interactions between anthropogenic and natural atmospheric constituents and
705 their importance for ACI under post-fossil conditions.

706 *Exploiting the unintended experiment posed by strong decadal trends in East Asian and natural*
707 *aerosols:* During the satellite era, East Asia has undergone rapid industrialization and economic
708 growth, and their associated anthropogenic aerosol emissions from fossil fuel usage, followed
709 by a highly successful cleanup effort, especially in China, since around 2010 (Samset et al.
710 2025). These strong, decadal scale emission trends have been well monitored, especially in later
711 decades, and form a natural testbed for hypotheses regarding the local and remote climate
712 effects of anthropogenic aerosol emissions (Li, 2020; Persad et al. 2023). On top, Eastern North
713 American emission declines as well as the IMO 2020 regulations have also been a useful cases.
714 Concurrently, global warming has increased rates of natural aerosol emissions, including e.g.
715 wildfire and sea spray emissions in the same regions (Mahowald et al., 2024; Kok et al., 2023,
716 Gali et al., 2019; Pernov et al., 2024a,b). This conjunction represents a golden opportunity for
717 probing cloud microphysics, atmospheric energetics, aerosol-precipitation processes, and more.
718 While the community is already broadly exploiting this unintended experiment, there are still
719 broad opportunities here when combined with the other avenues for advancement listed in this
720 section.

721 3.6. Advancing machine learning applications in ACI research

722 Machine learning offers new opportunities for advancing ACI research by enabling more
723 efficient analysis of satellite and climate model data, improving model parameterizations, and
724 exploring previously unexplored scenarios. However, challenges remain in integrating machine
725 learning models with physical climate models. Future steps should focus on:

726 *Improving satellite retrievals:* ML has the potential to revolutionize satellite data processing by
727 addressing the limitations of traditional retrieval methods (Wei et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022).
728 Machine learning techniques can be used to develop new retrieval algorithms that account for
729 non-linear relationships between observed satellite radiances and cloud properties. For
730 instance, machine-learned retrievals could improve the accuracy of cloud property estimates,
731 especially in regions with broken clouds, where standard retrieval techniques often fail
732 (Gryspeerdt, 2022), also utilizing ground-based data for more accurate algorithms (Kim et al.,
733 2021). They may also facilitate retrieval of previously inaccessible properties, such as CCN by
734 training on extensive aircraft campaign data (Redemann and Gao, 2024). Further development
735 of machine learning models for satellite data processing will be critical for refining global ACI
736 estimates and reducing uncertainties in climate models.

737 *Advancing the analysis of earth observations and models:* Applications of computer vision
738 transforms previously highly labour intensive studies, such as detection and labelling of ship-
739 tracks in satellite data (Watson-Parris et al., 2022, Yuan et al., 2022), from case studies to global
740 monitoring across the entire satellite record. Causal approaches facilitate disentangling of

741 causal relationships from confounding factors in studies of aerosol cloud interactions in models
742 (Fons et al, 2024) and observations (Jesson et al., 2022).

743 *Incorporating physical constraints into machine learning models:* While machine learning
744 models are useful for improving satellite data retrievals and improving model
745 parameterizations, they must incorporate physical constraints to ensure their validity for long-
746 term climate projections. Machine learning tools that include physical constraints are emerging
747 as a promising solution (Eyring et al., 2024). Hybrid modeling systems that combine climate
748 models with machine learning can simulate aerosol effects, including ACI, with greater accuracy
749 and efficiency, helping to reduce uncertainties in climate predictions.

750 *Developing climate model emulators:* Machine learning tools called emulators that are trained
751 on climate model data can significantly speed up climate modeling by predicting global
752 distributions of climate variables, such as temperature and precipitation, for given aerosol
753 emission scenarios. These emulators can efficiently probe previously unexplored scenarios,
754 allowing researchers to explore the impacts of different levels of anthropogenic and natural
755 aerosol emissions on cloud properties and climate (Watson-Parris et al., 2022).

756 3.7. Improving communication and collaboration across ACI research communities

757 Improved collaboration between satellite data analysts, climate modelers, and ground
758 based observational data experts and scientists, and hence training of the next-generation
759 atmospheric and climate scientists, is essential for advancing ACI research. Future efforts
760 should focus on building cross-disciplinary teams and enhancing data sharing to bridge existing
761 gaps in ACI knowledge. Key actions include:

762 *Fostering cross-disciplinary research:* ACI research requires collaboration across multiple
763 disciplines, including satellite observations, which can provide frequent measurements with
764 broad coverage, ground based and aircraft measurements, which can offer much greater detail,
765 and on spatial and temporal scales unobtainable from space, and climate modeling, which can
766 embed the measurements in a theoretical framework that represents current understanding,
767 and can calculate and extrapolate derived quantities. Efforts to foster communication between
768 these communities will ensure that insights from one area inform the others (Kahn et al., 2023).
769 For example, ground based remote sensing and in-situ measurements will be required to
770 constrain many physical and chemical processes involved in ACI, and satellite data can then be
771 used to map out in space and time the distribution of regimes where these processes occur,
772 thus placing the global occurrence of ACI processes on more solid ground. Models are needed
773 to help interpret satellite data and to generate predictions about future climate responses to
774 aerosol emissions.

775 *Expanding data accessibility:* Initiatives like AERONET and ACTRIS provide high-quality, real-
776 time data on aerosol optical properties and other key ACI variables (Lopatin et al., 2021).
777 Expanding the amount and accessibility of these datasets to a broader scientific community and
778 providing the key documentation to support its proper use for scientific investigation, will

779 enable more researchers to contribute to ACI studies, enhancing the collective understanding
780 of aerosol-cloud interactions. Efforts should continue to streamline data-sharing processes.

781 **5 Conclusions**

782 The global climate is rapidly changing, in response to a wide range of anthropogenic
783 emissions and other influences, with wide reaching consequences for society and nature.
784 Projecting and communicating the responses of the climate to past and future emissions, and
785 the efforts to mitigate them, is therefore among the most crucial tasks of the climate science
786 community today. We have shown how aerosol-cloud interactions remain a stubborn barrier to
787 providing precise and actionable advice to policy makers, at global, country and local levels.
788 This includes current and future rates of global warming, regional changes to temperature,
789 precipitation and extreme events, constraining the carbon budgets remaining before breaching
790 the temperature limits set out in the Paris Agreement and the Glasgow Pact, providing
791 information on the risks and potential benefits of Solar Radiation Modification, and linking
792 climate evolution to regional health issues.

793 Reducing uncertainties in aerosol-cloud interactions and therefore enabling the
794 scientific community and assessment bodies such as the IPCC, to give improved advice on these
795 and other topics, will require a multifaceted approach involving several subfields and leveraging
796 a range of emerging opportunities. We propose advances in all of these recommendations
797 summarized in Table 1, prioritizing those with immediate actions possible. These include
798 improving satellite data retrievals, expanding ground-based measurements, refining high-
799 resolution climate models, and advancing machine learning. Although some of these
800 suggestions align with existing efforts carried out from the global community, they need to
801 focus on natural and other aerosol sources that are emerging or anticipated to emerge in the
802 next decades (e.g., dust sources in polar regions, biomass burning aerosol and intensified
803 biological aerosol from the warming biosphere and new bioaerosol sources from areas
804 previously covered by ice) - as they will modulate clouds and cloud systems and contribute to
805 the structure of type of extreme events and impacts. Collaboration across research
806 communities and the strategic use of upcoming satellite missions will further enhance our
807 understanding of ACI processes, leading to better climate projections and more informed policy
808 recommendations.

809 In conclusion, we see the reduction of uncertainties on global and regional ACI - and
810 translating this knowledge into messaging of societal, stakeholder and policy maker relevance -
811 as a grand challenge for current climate science. Reductions in anthropogenic aerosol emissions
812 anticipated for the future do not imply that ACI will be less important, but rather that its
813 characteristics will change fundamentally in ways that need to be constrained for reliable
814 predictions and attributions with models. The coming years can see major developments and
815 breakthroughs, but only if ACI is kept at the forefront of the global research agenda.

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843

844 **Open Research**

845 Figure 1 is produced using numbers from the IPCC AR6 WG1 Chapter 7 (Forster et al., 2021).

846

847 **Conflict of Interest Disclosure**

848 The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest for this manuscript.

849

850 **References**

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1484 **Figure 1.** Aerosol-cloud interactions dominate the uncertainty on recent estimates of
 1485 anthropogenic surface temperature change. Left: Contributions to global mean surface
 1486 temperature (GSAT) change (1750-2019) from individual forcing components, including
 1487 uncertainties as assessed by the IPCC AR6. Right: Relative contribution to the total uncertainty
 1488 on historical GSAT change, estimated by re-calculating the uncertainty with one component
 1489 excluded. Rows are ordered from high to low contributions to the total GSAT change
 1490 uncertainty. All numbers from IPCC AR6 WG1 Chapter 7.

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1493 **Table 1.** Recommendations to address uncertainties and knowledge gaps in aerosol-cloud
 1494 interactions. Timescale shows when the recommended actions can result in improving our
 1495 understanding of ACI and/or their representation in weather and climate models.

Recommendations	Timescale
Improving Satellite Data and Retrieval Accuracy	
Reassessing satellite constraints (Dubovik et al., 2021)	Next 5-10 years
Combining ground based in-situ and remote sensing (Papagiannopoulos et al., 2016)	Next 1-5 years
Combining observations and models within data assimilation systems (Scheck et al., 2020)	Next 1-5 years
Enhancing Observational Campaigns and Ground-Based Measurements	
Expanding vertical profile measurements (Lopatin et al., 2021)	Next 10-20 years
Drones and balloons for in-situ profiling (Kahn et al., 2017)	Next 10-20 years
Systematic aircraft measurements of key aerosol properties and ACI processes (Kahn et al., 2017, 2023)	Next 5-10 years
Refining Climate Models to Accurately Simulate ACI	
Developing aerosol-aware, high-resolution models (Fosser et al., 2024)	Next 5-10 years
Process-based model evaluation (Blichner et al., 2024, Virtanen et al., 2025)	Next 1-5 years
Improved representations of aerosol size distributions and updrafts (Burgos et al., 2020)	Next 1-5 years
Leveraging Upcoming Satellite Missions for ACI	
Maximizing data from EarthCARE and PACE (Wehr et al., 2023; Werdell et al., 2019)	Next 5-10 years
Utilizing new polarimetric instruments (Hasekamp et al., 2019a,b)	Next 5-10 years
Long-term monitoring via METOP-SG and CO2M (Dubovik et al., 2019)	Next 10-20 years

Focusing on Post-Fossil Natural Aerosols	
Improving understanding of natural aerosol (Schmale et al., 2021)	Next 1-5 years
Improving understanding of interactions within and between natural and post-fossil anthropogenic aerosols (Sharma et al., 2019; Dada et al., 2022)	Next 1-5 years
Investigating aerosol-cloud feedbacks (Yli-Juuti et al., 2021; Gong et al., 2023)	Next 1-5 years
Laboratory studies of cloud relevant properties for natural aerosol and cloud microphysical processes (NASEM, 2016)	Next 1-5 years
Exploiting the unintended experiment posed by strong decadal trends in East Asian and natural aerosols (Samset et al., 2025)	Next 1-5 years
Advancing Machine Learning Applications in ACI Research	
Incorporating physical constraints into ML models (Eyring et al., 2024)	Next 1-5 years
Developing climate model emulators (Watson-Parris et al., 2022)	Next 5-10 years
ML for satellite retrieval algorithms (Kim et al., 2021)	Next 1-5 years
Improving Communication and Collaboration Across ACI Research Communities	
Fostering cross-disciplinary research (Kahn et al., 2023)	Immediate
Expanding data accessibility (Lopatin et al, 2021)	Immediate

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